

Effects of Play-way Teaching strategies on Cognitive and Social Skills Development among public Primary School Pupils in Ogun state.

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of play-way teaching strategies on Cognitive and Social Skills development among primary school pupils in Ogun state, Nigeria. Quasi-experimental research design was adopted for the study. Population of the study consists of all primary school class six pupils during the 2024/2025 academic session among public primary schools in Ogun State, Nigeria. A sample size of 154 pupils were selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique. Cronbach Alpha was used to validate play way teaching strategies on cognitive and social skills development at index of 0.821. Moderating variables of Gender and attitude of learners were examined on the outcome variable. Data were analyzed, using inferential statistics of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result shows a significant effect of play-way teaching strategies on cognitive skills development among Primary School pupils. Also, there is no significant main effect of gender on cognitive skills development among Primary School pupils. Lastly, there is no significant main effect of gender on Social Skills development among Primary School pupils in Ogun East Senatorial District. It was concluded from findings of the study that play way teaching strategy had significant effect on cognitive and social skills development of primary school pupils. Based on the finding of the study, a step-by-step user-friendly teaching guides on play way strategies should be designed by teachers to enhance the readiness and interest of primary school pupils towards learning.

Keywords: Play way teaching strategy, cognitive skill, social skill, primary school pupils.

Introduction

Primary education is a basic level of teaching and learning for economic, political, social and cultural empowerment of learners, necessary for poverty alleviation and transformation of lives. At this level, beginners are often confronted with learning challenges, often traced to inappropriate and monotonous method of instruction, which could interfere with their ability to acquire knowledge and skills for foundation building and general development. There is need for teachers to adopt relevant and purposeful teaching strategies that will not only improve academic performance, but promote learners' readiness and inspire them for critical cognitive and social skills development. Social skills development in children is essential and plays important role in their learning and academic activities. Holistic development which comprises cognitive, affective, and psychomotor is expected in every child from birth until adulthood. Cognitive skill can simply be regarded as the skill acquired by individuals from birth till death which runs through some stages described by Jean Piaget (1896 - 1980), Swiss Psychologist who discovered cognitive development in children. He identified the four stages of cognitive development which include sensorimotor stage preoperational stage, concrete operational stage, and formal operational stage which runs from 12 years and above (McLeod, 2020). Cognition itself is characterized by reasoning, that is, the ability to process activities through thinking and thereby actualizing or creating the thought. The function of cognition in development shows how information is being received, integrated, processed, and responded to through processes like divergent thinking, attention memory, convergent thinking, and executive function. These processes aid the learning activities of children whenever a concept is being introduced either within or outside the classroom and they aid the development of problem solving and critical thinking.

Apart from cognitive building, social skills development in children is essential and plays important role in their learning and academic activities It focuses on different ways by which children relate and interact with their social environment which includes the school, home, religious organization, peer gathering, associations, and so on. Social skill development has

the potential to aid children in developing all other skills like cognitive and psychomotor from the view that when a child is endowed with the ability to relate with others, either young or old, they have the cause to interact and exchange ideas which brings about reasoning; in the same vein, they engage in activities that improve both fine and gross motor (Rusmayadi & Herman, 2019). Social skill is described by Maleki, Mardani, Chehrzad, Dianatinasab, & Vaismoradi (2019) as being so essential in every child, as it enhances their mental wellness which is seen in the manner of relationship in the society, children's behaviourism, social competency, and response to social rules. It is therefore believed that when social skills are not well developed, children face the consequence of loneliness, emotional unrest, poor relationship and interaction skill, and social maladjustment. Cognitive and social skills development of pupils during early childhood stage underscores the core elements of their learning experience towards adulthood.

It is pertinent to identify the appropriate and relevant strategies teachers are to consider and select in order to make learning more meaningful for achievement of instructional objectives. There are other methods of teaching Primary school pupils, but the selection of the most suitable to learners' abilities, age and interest should be scientifically determined. Hence, play way and project-based teaching strategies are two of the most effective teaching methods for contents delivery for pupils in Primary schools. Ogunyemi and Ragpot, (2015), Akinyo, Oladele and Ebuta (2018) observed that play is something that occurs in children naturally, and is regarded as children's world. They opinionated that it is the fundamental reason they enjoy playing at anytime and anywhere. Young children benefit from play because it helps them to develop holistically. It is a self-directed activity where new skills and ideas can be practiced.

Through play, children make sense of the world in which they live (Ogunyemi and Ragpot, 2015). They try different ideas, it makes them to be aware of their strengths, which helps to develop their affective and psycho-motor domains (Anderson-McNamee, 2010). As children play, they understand better what socialization, relationship, gender, status, interaction, environment and other things mean. In some instances, children can express their emotions, worries or concerns while playing instead of discussing it with an adult. Hence, play is capable of helping children to express themselves better and enhance their physical, mental, social and emotional development (Ogunyemi and Henning, 2020).

A curriculum that incorporates playway strategy is required for a successful and memorable teaching and learning process. When play activity is initiated by children, they will be willing to learn and show positive dispositions to learning. Teachers' role in promoting playway learning strategy is very crucial because as children play, teachers ought to observe in order to ensure that the strategy is not abused, and to determine whether pupils are making good use of it. Therefore, the study was conducted to investigate the effect of Play way teaching strategy on cognitive and social skills development of Primary school pupils in Ogun East Senatorial District of Ogun State, Nigeria. Gender is said to be the economic, social, political and cultural attributes and opportunities associated with being women and men. The social definitions of what it means to be a woman or man vary among cultures and change overtime. Gender is cultural expression of particular characterizes and roles that are associated with certain groups of people with reference to their sex and sexuality.

There has been a great concern about the gradual loss of play during teaching and learning processes in Primary schools as revealed by literature. This is also being advocated for in schools in Nigeria. Hence, Primary school teachers need to consider a paradigm shift from the popular or common conventional style of teaching Primary school pupils as a routine. Research findings have shown that teachers adopt teaching strategies with little or no knowledge about their relevance to lesson contents (Mupa and Chinooneka 2015, Han, 2021). And when wrong teaching strategies are used to teach concepts without considering the relevant ones, ineffective learning outcomes could be obtained especially in the acquisition of social and cognitive skills. This is the reason American Academy of Paediatrics (AAP) released a report that appeals to families, schools, communities to bring back play to children's lives. In addition, the adoption of play way strategies appear to be limited during teaching and learning process in Primary schools. Many researches have been conducted on the use of play in developing cognitive skills of children, but the use of play strategies to develop social and cognitive skills of learners has hardly been investigated. There is no evidence that it is widely adopted by teachers, in spite of their relevance to effective learning outcomes. Therefore, there is need for teachers to adopt teaching strategies that will not only improve academic performance, but promote learners' critical thinking abilities and social interaction. It is on this premise that the researcher believed that play way teaching strategies could bring about the development of social and cognitive skills in Primary school pupils, using gender as a moderating variable.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to investigate the effect of play way teaching strategy on cognitive and social skills development of Primary school pupils in Ogun East Senatorial District of Ogun state, Nigeria. Therefore, the following specific objectives of the study were achieved;

1. To investigate the main effect of play way teaching strategy on cognitive skill development of Primary school pupils in Ogun state
2. To investigate the main effect of play way teaching strategy on social skill development of Primary school pupils in Ogun state
3. To determine the main effect of gender on cognitive skill development of Primary school pupils in Ogun state.
4. To examine the main effects of gender on social skill development of Primary school pupils in Ogun state

Hypotheses

1. There is no main effect of play way on Cognitive Skills Development among Primary School pupils in in Ogun state
2. There is no significant main effect of gender on Cognitive Skills development among Primary School pupils in Ogun East Senatorial District
3. There is no significant main effect of play way on Social Skills development among Primary School pupils in Ogun East Senatorial District.
4. There is no significant main effect of gender on Social Skills development among Primary School pupils in Ogun East Senatorial District

Methodology

This study is a quasi-experimental research design. It is a pretest-posttest non-equivalent control group design. It was carried out in Ogun East Senatorial District of Ogun State. The population of the study comprised of public primary school pupils in Ogun State. 474 public primary schools are in Ogun East Senatorial District and a sample size of 154 pupils were selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was modified pupils cognitive and social skill development questionnaire Attitude Towards Play way Teaching Strategy (APTSQ), Social Skill Questionnaire (SSQ) rating Cognitive Development Skills (CSQ) rating scale, Gender on Cognitive Skills Questionnaire (GCSQ), Gender on Social Skills Development Questionnaire (GSSQ). The instrument has 2 sections, A and B. Section A has demographic data information of participants while B contains items on 4 rating scale which are divided into strongly Agree 4, Agree – 3, Disagree -2, strongly disagree 1 which amount to 30 items. The items in section B were measured on a 4-point scale, strongly Agree 4, Agree – 3, Disagree -2, strongly disagree 1. The instruments validity was determined by experts. Cronbach alpha was used to determine the internal consistency of pupils cognitive and social skills development Social Skill Questionnaire (SSQ), Cognitive Development Skills (CSQ) which yielded alpha values of 0.05. The location of the sampled schools necessitated the involvement of some trained teachers by the researcher. They served as research assistants on the use of play way teaching strategy. Instrument on pupils cognitive and social skills development rating scale. Social Skill Questionnaire (SSQ), Cognitive Development Skills (CSQ) were administered to the participants in the treatment and control groups for pretest data collection. After administering pretest instruments to both experimental and control groups, treatment package on play way teaching strategy was given, sticking strictly to the instructional guide prepared on Home Economics. Also, participants in the control group were conventionally taught without play way method of teaching. The classes for subjects in the treatment group and the control group were held during the normal time on the time table of the schools. Each group was taught for 40 minutes each day twice a week, for 8weeks. After intervention, instruments administered at pretest were re-administered to the participants in the experimental and control groups, to generate post-test data. Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Table 1: Main effect of treatment on Cognitive Skills development among Primary School pupils.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant main effect of play way on Cognitive Skills development among Primary School pupils in Ogun East Senatorial District. To test this hypothesis, Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was carried out and the result is presented in Table 1a.

Table 1a: Tests of Between-Subjects Effects Dependent Variable: Posttest Cognitive Skills

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	2902.055 ^a	12	241.838	4.075	.000	.257
Intercept	6479.167	1	6479.167	109.170	.000	.436
Pretest cog	224.573	1	224.573	3.784	.054	.026
Treatment	1396.988	2	698.494	11.769	.000	.143
Gender	38.169	1	38.169	.643	.424	.005
Attitude	497.463	1	497.463	8.382	.004	.056
Treatment * Gender	102.796	2	51.398	.866	.423	.012
Treatment * Attitude	27.168	2	13.584	.229	.796	.003
Gender * Attitude	10.975	1	10.975	.185	.668	.001
Trt * Gender * Attitude	.515	2	.258	.004	.996	.000
Error	8368.282	141	59.350			
Total	1474258.000	154				
Corrected Total	11270.338	153				

a. R Squared = .257 (Adjusted R Squared = .194) (Field Work, 2024)

Main effect of play way on Cognitive Skills Development among Primary School pupils in Ogun state.

Hypothesis 1

The hypothesis states that there is no main effect of play way on Cognitive Skills Development among Primary School pupils in Ogun East Senatorial District.

Table 1b: Dependent Variable: Posttest Cognitive Skills Estimates

Instructional Strategies adopted	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Play way Strategy	99.721 ^a	1.071	97.604	101.838
Conventional Strategy	92.891 ^a	1.146	90.625	95.157

a. Covariates appearing in the model are evaluated at the following values: Pretest Cognitive Skills = 96.3506. (Field Work, 2024)

The Estimated Marginal Means of **Tables 1b** gives the adjusted means (controlling for the covariate 'Pretest') for each group. From the data in the EMM, Tables 1, the Grand Mean is 97.479 for Cognitive Skills development among Primary School pupils in Ogun East Senatorial District. The data in Tables 1 revealed that the Experimental Group had a mean score of 99.721, the Control group (Conventional Teaching Strategy) had an adjusted mean of 92.891. This indicates that the Experimental Group performed better than the Control group confirming that treatment had differential effects on Cognitive Skills development among Primary School pupils in Ogun East Senatorial District. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no main effect of treatment on Cognitive Skills Development among Primary School pupils in Ogun East Senatorial District was rejected.

Main effect of Gender on Cognitive Skills development among Primary School pupils.

Hypothesis 2

The hypothesis states that there is no significant main effect of gender on Cognitive Skills development among Primary School pupils in Ogun East Senatorial District.

The data in Table 2 revealed that there is no significant main effect of gender on Cognitive Skills development among Primary School pupils in Ogun East Senatorial District. ($F_{(1,141)} = 0.643$ $P > .05 = 0.424$). Based on this result, hypothesis 2 was not rejected. Estimated Marginal Means. Hence, there is no significant main effect of gender on Cognitive Skills development among Primary School pupils in Ogun East Senatorial District

Table 2: Dependent Variable: Post-test Cognitive Skills Estimates

Sex of Pupils	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Male	96.965 ^a	.932	95.124	98.807
Female	97.992 ^a	.874	96.265	99.719

a. Covariates appearing in the model are evaluated at the following values: Pretest Cognitive Skills = 96.3506. (Field Work, 2024)

Table 3: Main effect of play way on Social Skills Development among Primary School pupils in Ogun East Senatorial District

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant main effect of play way on Social Skills development among Primary School pupils in Ogun state.

Table 3a: Tests of Between-Subjects Effects Dependent Variable: post test Social

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	4799.706 ^a	12	399.975	6.372	.000	.352
Intercept	4122.308	1	4122.308	65.677	.000	.318
Pretest Soc	663.698	1	663.698	10.574	.001	.070
Treatment	764.467	2	382.234	6.090	.003	.080
Gender	.858	1	.858	.014	.907	.000
Attitude	532.484	1	532.484	8.484	.004	.057
Treatment * Gender	147.542	2	73.771	1.175	.312	.016
Treatment * Attitude	614.544	2	307.272	4.895	.009	.065
Gender * Attitude	95.969	1	95.969	1.529	.218	.011
Trt * Gender * Attitude	233.003	2	116.501	1.856	.160	.026
Error	8850.061	141	62.766			
Total	1434066.000	154				
Corrected Total	13649.766	153				

a. R Squared = .352 (Adjusted R Squared = .296) (Field Work, 2024)

Table 3b: Dependent Variable: Posttest Social Skills Development Estimates

Sex of Pupils	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Male	95.852 ^a	.961	93.951	97.752
Female	95.698 ^a	.898	93.923	97.472

a. Covariates appearing in the model are evaluated at the following values: Pretest Social = 94.5195. (Field Work, 2024)

From the data above, the grand mean is 95.775 for Social Skills development among Primary School pupils in Ogun East Senatorial District. The data in Table 4 revealed that the males had a mean score of 95.852 and the females had an adjusted mean of 95.698. With this result, the males had a better post test Social Skills development mean score among Primary School

pupils but from ANCOVA this was not significant. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the Social Skills development among Primary School pupils across gender and so **hypothesis 3** was not rejected. From the Partial Eta Squared Value Table 6, gender did not contribute to the variance in the dependent variable.

Hypothesis 4: This hypothesis states that there is no significant main effect of gender on Social Skills development among Primary School pupils in Ogun East Senatorial District. The data in Table 4.13 revealed that there is no significant main effect of gender on Social Skills development among Primary School pupils in Ogun East Senatorial District. ($F_{(1,141)} = 0.014 P > .05 = 0.907$). Based on this result, hypothesis 2(b) was not rejected. Estimated Marginal Means,

Table 4, was determined to examine the differences in the post test means of the two categories of gender.

Table 4. Main effect of Gender on Social Skills development among Primary School pupils.

Table 4a: Dependent Variable: Post test Social Skills Development Estimates

Sex of Pupils	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Male	95.852 ^a	.961	93.951	97.752
Female	95.698 ^a	.898	93.923	97.472

a. Covariates appearing in the model are evaluated at the following values: Pretest Social = 94.5195. (Field Work, 2024)

Table 4b: Dependent Variable: Post test Social Skills Estimates

Attitude Level	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
High Attitude	97.908 ^a	.953	96.025	99.792
Low Attitude	93.641 ^a	1.013	91.639	95.643

(Field Work, 2024)

Discussion of Findings

Findings from data generated indicated that there was significant effect of Play way teaching strategy on Cognitive Skills development among Primary School pupils in Ogun state. This was in line with the findings of Akinyo, Oladele and Ebuta (2018) who observed that play is something that occurs in children naturally, and it is regarded as children's world. They opinionated that children benefit from play because it helps them to develop holistically. It is a self-directed activity where new skills and ideas can be practiced. Through play children can express their mind freely, it gives children opportunity to investigate, make mistakes, explore and use trial and error. In a similar study on influence of play on cognitive development of school children, Samuelsson & Carlsson (2008) concluded in their findings that during play way strategy, different materials given to children to explore could promote learning, which could also facilitate cognitive learning outcome while they play.

Also, Ogunnaiya, Mustapha-Dokunmu & Morenikeji (2021) and Asmara and Rulyansah (2024), concluded that undirected play allows children to learn how to work in groups, to share, to negotiate, to resolve conflicts, and to learn self-advocacy skills. When play is allowed to be child driven, children practice decision-making skills, move at their own pace, discover their own areas of interest, and ultimately engage fully in the passions they wish to pursue. In the view of Coolahan, Fantuzzo, Mendez & McDermott (2000), play is considered as an integral part of the academic environment. Awopetu (2024), expressed further that through play the school setting attends to the social and emotional development of children as well as their cognitive development. It has helped children adjust to the school setting and to enhance their learning readiness, behaviour, and problem-solving skills. Social-emotional learning is best integrated with academic learning through play and interaction of children, which enhance their ability to learn. (Mona, Manal and Amani, 2019, Welding, 2022 & Becker, 2023).

Burgess & Ernst, (2020) and Awopetu (2024), supporting the view of Coolahan, Fantuzzo, Mendez & McDermott (2000), concluded that play and unscheduled time that allow for peer interactions are important components of social-emotional learning. Therefore, play way teaching strategy is a relevant strategy for building cognitive capacity of primary school learners.

Conclusion

Play way teaching strategy was found to have significant effect on cognitive and social skills development of primary school pupils. The study indicated significant difference in pretest and post test mean scores of the participants who received treatment on Play way strategies than the participants in the control group. There was a significant main effect of attitude on cognitive and Social Skills development. The study revealed that there was no significant effect of gender on Cognitive and Social Skills development.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following are recommended;

1. Play way teaching strategy should be used by teachers for cognitive and social skills development of primary school pupils.
2. Teachers should work out modalities for inculcating positive attitude towards learning, when selecting teaching strategies for achievement of learning outcomes.
3. A step by step user friendly teaching guides on play way strategies should be designed by teachers to enhance the readiness and interest of primary school pupils towards learning

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